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Post-US withdrawal Afghanistan: Problems and prospects

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Abstract

Afghanistan has always been a bone of contention either amongst its local tribes or foreign forces but it has never been fully occupied and controlled either by any particular native tribe or any foreign invader. Foreign invasion of a country often leaves the invaded country in security, social, economic and humanitarian crises after the withdrawal of the invaders. This study was designed to explore the possible causes of US withdrawal from Afghanistan in 2020, and the ascendancy of Taliban to the government and the political, social, economic and humanitarian impacts of US withdrawal on the people of Afghanistan and the ultimate possible prospects for the Taliban government, the people of the country and international community. Relevant secondary data was collected from research articles in newspapers and was thoroughly analyzed through the Content Analysis Technique. It was found out from the analyses that the US withdrawal posed severe social, political and economic impacts on the people of Afghanistan. It was further found that US withdrawal once again took the country into humanitarian crises including food insecurity, poverty, unemployment, bad law-and-order and brain-drainage, social disharmony, political polarization and economic recession. For this purpose, the researcher has adopted the Regional Security Complex Theory where it proposes that the internal security dynamics and the civil wars along with the social, political and humanitarian crises outburst in the state of Afghanistan. The study also identified a number of potential prospects of Taliban take-over for the people of Afghanistan and the international community if the international players persuade them to observe international obligations and protect human rights and extend political recognition to Taliban government and financial assistance to Afghan government.

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Keywords: post-US-withdrawal, Taliban government, social, political and economic impacts, political polarization, social disharmony.

Introduction

Afghanistan has always been a bone of contention either amongst its local tribes or foreign states but it has never been fully occupied and controlled either by any particular native tribe or any foreign invader. Foreign invasion of a country often leaves the invaded country in security, social, economic and humanitarian crises after the withdrawal of the invaders. The history of Afghanistan shows that the rule of every native tribe or foreign invader was followed by numerous problems and resistance. The state went through civil-wars or political instability, political maneuvering, social upheaval and economic degradation. In the previous five decades Afghanistan was invaded and held for a period of time by two world super-powers: USSR and The United States of America but none of them either occupied it fully or brought political stability and integration. Both the super-powers invaded the country to install a stable and internationally recognized government

but their hasty withdrawal from the country ultimately led to unimaginable political and social polarization and economic degradation. This study has been designed to explore the possible causes of US withdrawal from Afghanistan in 2020, and the ascendancy of Taliban to the government and its political, social, economic and humanitarian impacts on the people of Afghanistan and the ultimate prospects for the people of the country and international community.

Afghanistan lies in the heart of Asia and more specifically the South-Central Asia. It is a landlocked country and therefore, has no access to sea-waters of its own. Many of the empires came and went but there were none to keep hold on it for many years or centuries just like many other states of the world because of its population. They are considered toughest and hardest human beings on the land. It has been given the name of "Graveyard of the Empires". The quality of the name is for the reason that many empires had burnt their esteem and dignity here and left their countries with defeat. It has the most dubious and vague past (Jones, 2009).

Barfield (2010) adds that Afghanistan was mostly entangled within its fractious rivalries. Within a single tribe, there have been many more sub clans who had fought wars and had an animosity between and among them. These fractious wars led to many internal rifts among various clans and in a short span, many of the clans had ruled here. Unity was absent in the single tribe mostly. British in the World War-I borne the heavy loss of men and resources due to which they became weak in this regard. They could not run their colony smoothly and efficiently as they used to run in the pre-war era. Now in 1919-21 the 3rd battle of Anglo-Afghan war fought in which British faced the brunt of defeat. In this war, Afghanistan was declared independent from the British influence and Amanullah declared the country a monarchy rather than an emirate or republic in 1926 (PBSO, 2011).

After the fall of king Aman Ullah, Nadir Shah was made the new king by the local chieftains. He did possess great military skills, was well-equipped administrator and ran effective determination to lead the country in a positive way (Wahab, 2007). Then, Wahab (2007) further elaborates the reign of King Zahir who

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ascended the throne in 1933 and ruled Afghanistan for 40 years. He was groomed by his father and prepared for the reign. He ruled Afghanistan but just by name. His time was the era of Second World War and the Cold war. Next in the row is, Muhammad Daood who replaced Mehmood as premier in 1953 and later, ousted Zahir from kingship in 1973, was on exile to Rome till 2002 when he rejuvenated his ideas to help the Kabul government in its administrative and political aspects (Lee, 2018).

Olam (n.d) says that after the withdrawal of Soviet Union from Afghanistan, the country welcomed the Taliban. The country faced multiple problems including the civil war which led to more devastation. People happily welcomed the advent of Taliban forces to install the government. After the rule of about five years, the Al-Qaeda organization attacked the USA soil by hijacking four planes which led to the toppling of the Taliban government. The United States along with Northern Alliance launched military campaign against the Taliban government. The United Nation Security Council had approved the sending and deployment of International Security Assistance Forces (ISAF) to Afghanistan. Rubin (2013) Says that the response of Taliban along its ally Al-Qaeda to the US invasion also causes devastating destruction to the Northern areas Shamali plains of Afghanistan. That area was once used to be the greenest areas of Afghanistan. Many peasants were living there and many of them were farmers. The Shamali plain which was a fertile land with sufficient water supply for irrigation and was chiefly farmed by the Tajik peasants.

Although, the attacks and deteriorating situation in Afghanistan did not come to an end. The situation under the close watch of UN assistance workers and the USA's leadership, the attacks increased instead of decreasing. During Taliban regime in 2001, no such attacks occurred but increased by, data taken from the Centre on International Cooperation, four, ten and sixteen in the following years till 2003. Data collected by the Afghan NGO Security Office (ANSO) on killings of all NGO staff shows thirteen killed in 2003 and twenty-one killed in January–August 2004, many of them in connection with election preparation rather than humanitarian work (Rubin, 2013).

Hamid (2022) writes that as the US and NATO have started withdrawing from Afghanistan, the Taliban regrouped and started attacks on the Afghan National Security Forces (ANSF). There have been reported that the Taliban have abducted, put to death and having been injured the Afghan soldiers. This showed the real potentials and their abilities to cope with the writ of the government. People were already fed up from the corrupt practices and malpractices of the government's institutions and the elite class of the country. Hamid M. W (2020) write that after the reports of NATO withdrawal emerged on the scene, the anarchy and disturbance have surged in 34 provinces of the country. The insurgent groups and the resisted groups have got momentum in their activities in the absence of NATO forces. The ISIS have recruited the dissent members of Taliban ranks in their forces. The ISIS have taken the responsibility of bombing in Jalalabad which has killed dozens of innocent people.

The scenario changed after the USA presidential election hinges over the heads of American. The November 2016 presidential election brought unprecedented foreign policy changes for Afghanistan. The Donald Trump promises in his election campaigns to bring back the troops home was a decisive policy

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(Nourzhanov, 2021). He further argued that the situation in Afghanistan further aggravated under the auspice of President Trump. Political and security situation deteriorated. By 2018, Trump have decided to pull out US troops from Afghanistan is the better option. His administration realized that the peace is to be achieved only through political means bringing the Taliban to a negotiating table and peace deal (Global Conflict Tracker, 2022).

Research Questions

Q1: What problems will arise in Afghanistan after the US withdrawal? Q2: what are the prospects of Taliban's takeover for Afghanistan?

Research Objectives

1. To analyze the possible social, political and economic impacts of US withdrawal on Afghanistan.
2. To explore and highlight the prospects of Taliban's takeover of Afghanistan after US withdrawal.

Significance of Research

Since long, Afghanistan is the central point and cockpit where different parts of Asia connect to each other. The prosperity in the region is mostly dependent upon stable Afghanistan. As we are witnessing that Afghanistan is going through a dreadful time which has grieved impacts internally as well externally. One cannot think of open trade and safe land routes through Afghanistan where millions of people are going through starvation and poverty.

The study will be of paramount importance for international political leaders, policy makers and think-tanks to evaluate the on-going humanitarian, political and economic crises in Afghanistan in the aftermath of US withdrawal. The study will help international political community and academicians to highlight the plight of Afghani people in international community and turn the attention of the international political players to take notice of the humanitarian, political and economic crises in Afghanistan and play their role in saving humanity from another civil war, starvation, ignorance and political instability in Afghanistan.

Literature Review

Afghanistan have seen a turbulent history after the shocked and surprised invasion of USSR and the United States of America. Afghans' government is collapsed and the international community is still shocked and surprise by the rapid victory of the Taliban (Daily Times, 2021). The War-on- terror which was started by the United States of America in 2001 after the shock incident of September 9, 2001. The US stepped into the most expensive war in its history to root out the master mind of 9/11 attacks. Later on, this objective was changed into the democracy building in Afghanistan. This brought unprecedented and unparalleled human and financial losses to the war- torn country along with the US and its NATO allies. This brought to their mind after about two decades that has been costly for them to make another state especially Afghanistan a democratic state. The US has spent \$2 trillion dollars in Afghanistan. Therefore, keeping in view the uselessness of the decade's long war, the US under Trump

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administration finally decided to withdraw from Afghanistan. For this reason, the Trump administration realized to have a political settlement rather than by force. Resultantly they compiled the agreement which was held after several rounds of talks in Doha, Qatar. Successfully, the agreement was signed between Taliban and US (Ijaz, 2021).

Ijaz (2021) furthermore, upon the deal in Doha signed between the Taliban and US pressed on the withdrawal of US and its allied forces to withdraw from Afghanistan. The same process happened and Kabul was left on the mercy of Taliban. Resultantly, the chaos and disturbance emerged on the eve of Taliban's succession into Kabul. As (Anwar, 2022) says that the Ukraine crisis has overshadowed Afghanistan in the news, the Afghan population is still facing acute food shortage, a crumbling economy, bleak law and order situation and rising unemployment. The USA has other problems and challenges to cope with which are the imminent than staying in Afghanistan fighting the longest and expensive war in its military history. As the U.S. has rightly focused on competition with great powers in Europe and the China Pacific (Mulroy, 2022).

Iqbal (2022) writes in his book about the other reason of withdrawal that the threat of Al-Qaeda has diminished from the soil of Afghanistan. They have come here for eradicating the Al-Qaeda organization which they have done. The third part of the deal provides and explains that the Taliban would not let the terrorist organizations use the Afghanistan soil against the US. As for the agreement was concern, the Taliban assured them regarding their soil to be not used by the Al-Qaeda or any other organization against the US and its allies. This has led and compelled the US to pull out her troops from Afghanistan. There was no other option for staying in Afghanistan. The war was already costly for them in respect to the humans' casualties and also economically tough for the Americans to lose their exchequer for nothing. The eradication of Al-Qaeda was the big aim of USA which she thought have diminished it. The recent killing of Al-Zawahiri is also a point in notice which they thought is the most influential person in Al-Qaeda. He was killed in drone attack after the Taliban have taken the Kabul in their gripe. Resultantly, the last threat was also dreadfully removed which they have taken the sigh of relief.

Iqbal (2022) further elaborates that another factor was the Peaceful withdrawal of the American forces. The Taliban would let the foreign troops out of Afghanistan peacefully. They will not attack on the foreign troops and the agreement was also signed for this reason that the Taliban would cease the fire for some time to let the US forces out of Afghan soil. In the other way around, they have promised the USA's authority that they would respect women in their society and rule and would not deal them as happened in the previous term of office in late 1990s. Lastly, the presence in the Afghan's territory is useless for them for the reason that the Al-Qaeda and other organizations' leaders have been killed by the US forces. Resultantly, they have planned for the withdrawal of their forces.

The drug trafficking was an issue for the international concerns. It created resentment among the community as it spoils the health of the world populations. On the one side, the US military had the capability to deal with the drug traffickers than the States Department but they were hesitant to spoil their relations with the traffickers and local warlords, as this was their only way of financing their plans. The CIA was disagreed to tackle the issue because they

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considered it aloof from their mission. Neither CIA nor the NATO were agreed to settle with drug traffickers. On the other hand, from 2004 to 2006, the number of insurgencies and bomb blasts were increased. These blasts were financed by the opium profits (Whitlock, 2021). Since the invasion of the US on Afghanistan, there has been much upheavals and chaos in the country. Their presence and the mission did not bring the instability and political turmoil to the stability in the country. It is not only the Taliban who are responsible for the destruction and political instability but the big powers and their allies are also connected to this chaos. The nation building in Afghanistan has been the concern for international community which had never fulfilled (Sinha, 2022).

There was a time when the American leaders have decided to withdraw from the soil of Afghanistan. By 2014, the American had withdrawn about 70% of its troops from Afghanistan. There was not any substantial victory for the American except the killing of Osama Bin Ladin in 2011. Almost everything perished in this unnecessary war in Afghanistan. This was the most expensive and a diplomatic blunder for the Americans in their military history. The war proved to be fatal for the American's dignity and national exchequer. The already diluted ethnic factions have created more fault lines in the Afghan's borders further aggravated the situation by inducing the Taliban movement coming from Uzbeks, Saudi and Pakistan to boost up the momentum of Taliban in Afghanistan. The recent attack on the parliament in Kabul and the takeover of the Taliban in the Kunduz region led to the dismantling of peace negotiation between Ashraf Ghani government and the Taliban government. (Sinha, 2022).

Hamid (2022) writes that as the US and NATO have started withdrawing from Afghanistan, the Taliban regrouped and started attacks on the Afghan National Security Forces (ANSF). There have been reported that the Taliban have abducted, put to death and having been injured the Afghan soldiers. This showed the real potentials and their abilities to cope with the writ of the government. People were already fed up from the corrupt practices and malpractices of the government's institutions and the elite class of the country. Even those who were living in the safe heavens of Pakistan's Ex-Federally Administered Tribal Areas (Ex-FATA) also fled to Afghanistan due to the Operation Zarb-e-Azab and were reorganize in the country. This has created more resentment and gave the momentum to the movement of Taliban. They launched the Spring Offensive against the government. The Taliban have also been reported to have kidnapped 9 border police in Bad-e- Ghais province.

Hamid M. W (2020) write that after the reports of NATO withdrawal emerged on the scene, the anarchy and disturbance have surged in 34 provinces of the country. The insurgent groups and the resisted groups have got momentum in their activities in the absence of NATO forces. The ISIS have recruited the dissent members of Taliban ranks in their forces. The ISIS have taken the responsibility of bombing in Jalalabad which has killed dozens of innocent people. The different and heinous attacks of the ISIS compelled the president of Afghanistan to say that the Islamic State of Khurasan Province (ISKP) is present on the land of Afghanistan and branded them with a name "Wolves" and precarious to the then Taliban. This insurgency has made the former army chief and vice president, Rashed Dostum to launch operations against this group. Other reports published in which it was mentioned that about 10000 attacks are being witnessed by the

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Afghanistan after the NATO and coalition forces withdrawal in 2015.

Nourzhanov (2021) argued that the situation in Afghanistan further aggravated under the auspice of President Trump. Political and security situation deteriorated. By 2018, Trump have decided to pull out US troops from Afghanistan is the better option. His administration realized that the peace is to be achieved only through political means bringing the Taliban to a negotiating table and peace deal. To do so, his administration stepped into the peace deal after so many turns and twists resulted the US-Taliban peace deal on 29 February Doha Deal, 2020.

Iqbal (2022) writes in his books that the peace deal was compiled by US-Taliban due to the unflinching and tireless efforts of Zalmi Khalilzad. This would open the intra-Afghan peace talks. During the negotiation, both the parties were agreed on some points. Initially, the Taliban committed to reduce the violence for seven days from 22 to 29 February and the US had to reduce the forces from 13000 to 8600 in the upcoming 135 days. Sanctions would be lift from Taliban and their prisoners to be released. The withdrawal of the foreign forces was the strict demand of the Taliban since their emergence as in insurgents. On the other hand, the Taliban will ensure to halt and obstruct the ways of Al-Qaeda, ISIS-K and other militant groups to use the Afghanistan soil against the US and its allies. Although, there were many traumatic events happened in which the Trump had denounced the Peace deal with Taliban in 2020. But after the deal was done in which the US forces withdrawn in a shameful and weird manner from Afghanistan.

The deal provided for the intra-Afghan negotiation to settle the internal conflicts and problems. After the short pause in the violence against the government the Taliban shortly resumed the attacks over the Afghan Security forces and civilians. The direct talks were started after a month of the deal but due to much delay in the part of the Afghan government and the subsequent attacks of the US forces on Taliban led the Taliban to capture the capital. Violence across Afghanistan continued in 2020 and 2021 (Global Conflict Tracker, 2022).

Theoretical Framework

The theory which is applied to the dissertation is the Regional Security Complex Theory expounded by Barry Buzan and Ole Waever. This theory covers the hasty withdrawal of the USA from Afghanistan and its weird impacts on the state of Afghanistan. The theoretical framework encircles the areas of domestic problems aroused from the hurried and hasty withdrawal of USA from Afghanistan. This theory provides an umbrella to the whole dissertation to groom under its shadow. As this theory suggests that the states inside the South Asian are divided into various factions like ethnicity, communal violence, political instability, economic deteriorated condition and the eruption of civil wars. Along with these, the disproportionate representation of the communities and deprivations of the human rights are vital in this theory and Afghanistan could be seen well in the prism of the Regional Security Complex Theory.

Looking to this perspective, analyzing the state of Afghanistan in the prism of Regional Security Complex Theory, it presents that greater states involve themselves in the affairs of other states. Thus, creates enormous problems and conflicts in the internal affairs of the concern state. As the Americans political

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aims and the withdrawal of the USSR forces postulates that they had had their own personal interests in Afghanistan. As the USSR withdrew from the Afghanistan in 1989, it left the country with unbridled social, economic, political and humanitarian crises. Following the suit, the USA also did the same in 2021 which led the Afghanistan's states into a quagmire of problems long lasting. As the initial phase of the security concern of the USA was to kill Osama Bin Ladin. But with the passing of time, her interests changed which has further exacerbated the country's situation. As the country was more disastrous to various issues like civil wars but the invasion of USA made it more deteriorate. Various terrorist groups like East Turkistan Islamic Movement and ISIS have used the fragility of Afghanistan to their favor and terror attacks have been committed since long (Tahir, 2022).

Analysis of the Data

The War-on-terror which was started by the United States of America in 2001 after the shock incident of September 9, 2001. The US stepped into the most expensive war in its history to root out the master mind of 9/11 attacks. Later on, this objective was changed into the democracy building in Afghanistan. This brought unprecedented and unparalleled human and financial losses to the war-torn country along with the US and its NATO allies. This brought to their mind after about two decades that has been costly for them to make another state especially Afghanistan a democratic state. The US has spent \$2 trillion dollars in Afghanistan. Therefore, keeping in view the uselessness of the decade's long war, the US under Trump administration finally decided to withdraw from Afghanistan. For this reason, the Trump administration realized to have a political settlement rather than by force. Resultantly they compiled the agreement which was held after several rounds of talks in Doha, Qatar. Successfully, the agreement was signed between Taliban and US. Afterwards, the Taliban have taken control of most of the areas in Afghanistan one after the others and soon captured Kabul on 15 August 2021 having been wiping out all the forces and rivals in Afghanistan.

Furthermore, upon the deal in Doha signed between the Taliban and US pressed on the withdrawal of US and its allied forces to withdraw from Afghanistan. The same process happened and Kabul was left on the mercy of Taliban. Resultantly, the chaos and disturbance emerged on the eve of Taliban's succession into Kabul. At the end of the 2021, Afghanistan emerged as the discussion topic on the theater of international stage. The world was so concern about the devastating and deteriorating situation in Afghanistan. The withdrawal created much tense in multiple grounds like humanitarian issues, political issues and economic issues. As increasing food scarcity and effects of economic sanctions imposed by the Western world, led by the United States.

The war imprints innumerable impacts on the society especially in the respects of socio-economic humanitarian and political aspects. A country like Afghanistan who has a warring past in the history became prey to all the problems emerge after the war. The same happened in the post-US withdrawal in 2021. Multifaceted problems and impacts emerged on the theater of Afghanistan's politics. After a month of the Taliban's take over in Afghanistan, the country faces drastic situation. The crises deteriorated day by day under the Taliban rule.

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Millions of people face starvation, health crises and wages are shrinking. The whole country having thirty-eight million population is terribly depends on the foreign aid before the Taliban. In the post-Taliban era, the international communities are concern and have reservations about the Taliban's rule which stopped most of the organizations and NGOs their humanitarian assistance and programs. Human rights abuses have only increased since the Taliban took over the country. They have overseen the public executions of dozens of people, an increase in threats against journalists and activists, a decline in girls attending school and a tightening of restrictions on women among other abuses.

Furthermore, the people of Afghanistan are already out of money and they do not have enough resources to get things for their daily life sustenance. There are only two percent of Afghans who have enough food to eat in the entire country. World Food Program and the UN organization have warned that the acute hunger can become widespread in the upcoming winter in Afghanistan. Overall, about three million children are suffering from malnutrition in Afghanistan overall. In Afghanistan half of the total population are in the dire need of food. They face intense hunger and starvation while the country has been in the tight grip of the droughts and famine in the decades of wars. According to estimates, during the last winter season, around 22.8 million people faced a 'high level of acute food insecurity' – which is around 55 percent of the total population of Afghanistan (Anwar, 2022).

The US has imposed much sanctions on the part of Taliban. They are suffering from sanctions. The condition of the state is not that much tightened to shoulder multiple problems at the same time. It is the US sanction which strongly affects the humanitarian issues inside Afghanistan. This situation created and threatened a mass exodus refugee from Afghanistan which had exacerbated the already dire humanitarian crisis. The displacement and humanitarian crises will increase more burdens on Afghanistan specifically and on neighbors generally. Since the Taliban have taken over, the fear of return to repressive policies and human rights violations against women and girls have once again arisen (Mosley, 2021). This seems so ambiguous in the field. Their rule came to a halt almost all of the Afghanistan. The jobs of female are just limited to the hospitals and nothing else. This can seriously make the gap between the male and female.

Indicators suggest that conditions have gone from bad to worse outwardly since August 2021: the World Food Program states that in August 2022 that 92% of Afghans reported not having enough to eat, an increase from the 80% of Afghans that had not enough food before the Taliban takeover. World Food Program have also presented their report in June that global food price increases and supply chain are prey to delays caused by the war in Ukraine are "having a direct impact on World

Food Program's Afghanistan operations." The United Nations Special Representative for Afghanistan said in March 2022 that due to emergency assistance from international donors, we have perhaps diverted the horrible fears of famine and widespread hunger. Even though the situation remains dreadful at the time being.

Other problem includes the banning of girls from school to get education. The Taliban have ordered the closure of the schools at different parts of the country. They did not give any clear solution as to what to be done afterwards when the

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decision was taken. Even Islam does not forbid the female of their rights to get education and do their jobs under the prescribed Sharia and laws. But the interpretation of the Taliban is different than the original one. As Hazrat Muhammad SAW said, "seek knowledge from cradle to the grave." This obviously shows the importance of education in Islam which seems that the Taliban's prescription of Sharia is not interpreted according to the Islam. They believe that the male must have to accompany them and the teachers should be female instead of male. The co-education is not allowed. For this purpose, the separate buildings are necessary to be given for the female education."

Another evidence of being an uneducated is, the mothers could never up bring their children if they do not have enough know-how about the daily life's problems. As the situation is already worst in Afghanistan in respect to the malnutrition and death during the times of baby birth. In this situation, they need to have some understandings of the pregnancies and that obviously comes by getting some degree of education. The parents can get to know about multiple problems and they may tackle them at home if they have enough understanding. "Malnutrition issues occur here are not because of economic challenges, but they are facing problems because their mothers are illiterate and do not know how to feed their children," said Samsor Zarin, a doctor in a hospital.

The Taliban regime is unable to engage international donors because of imposed sanctions, frozen assets by the US and European Union, and lack of recognition of the incumbent government by the world at large. The US has been at the forefront of the measures taken against the Taliban regime and views them as illegitimate and has, thus, imposed sanctions, denying them access to the country's assets and cash reserves abroad. This has led to the inability of the Afghan government to regulate the currency or pay its employees resulting in a crumbling economy, collapse of social order and an increase in corrupt practices. "The US froze country's \$7 billion following the Taliban takeover, resulting in a catastrophic economic crisis in the country. Some 10 million Afghans are at risk of poverty due to this decision to withhold the sum." Funds are the money on which a country runs. The assets are laid in the foreign banks. By these funds the country can run its affairs internally as well as externally.

The war-torn country does not have enough resources to give services to its citizens. The basic health care system is totally collapsed. Doctors, nurses and compounders are not paid. The basic facilities in the hospitals are vanished. Medicines are in scarcity. The doctors are not paid with their wages and the female nurses are obstructed to work in hospitals without their close male relative. This has boosted up more the crises in health system. The collapse emerges suddenly after the Afghanistan deals with outbreaks of diarrhea, COVID-19, malaria, measles and polio at the same time. Sometimes things are needed in hospitals which can be done by men more quickly and more efficiently than the women. For these reasons one cannot kick off the male compounders in hospitals. The system collapses when there is lack of male in the department.

Moreover, along with the above mentioned issues, there is gruesome issue of human security in Afghanistan. Despite the fact that the Taliban have taken over Afghanistan was so smooth but yet the situation and condition of the security of human lives are not that much satisfactory. Every second or third day, if not every day, some blasts or casualties occur which led people to shock especially the

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concern of international community. The horrible attacks carried out by the Islamic State in Khurasan Province (IS-K) on the airport of Kabul in the times of evacuation of the people. This scene had created the internal security challenges for the leadership inside the Taliban. The Taliban's warriors have to fight the irregular wars which is a serious blow to their security and governmental performance. Their performance comes under the serious questions when the innocent people are attacked by the suicide bomber.

Furthermore, under the auspice of Taliban, a common man does not feel himself to be safe in the country. This created the terrible fear in the hearts of citizens in time of crises. This has worsened the psychology of the people more than ever happened. Recently many of the women activists were dispersed after they have protested against the Taliban government. They feel insecure in the government of Taliban. As the international community is still on the way of judging the Taliban's hardliners for their repressive and inhuman policies in Afghanistan. The international community has the leverage to convince them on the fundamental rights of the woman and respect the commitments made by them in the Doha accord commitments to counter the terrorism. But at the same time, the recent development including the developments in the restrictions on the Afghanistan's women showed that the Taliban regime is not going to compromise on their fundamental ideological views and seems that they will not cooperate on their ultra-conservative outlook.

In addition to this, issues related to ethnicity are also on the peak. There is not a single ethnicity through which the system could run easily, but a confusing kind of situation is there. Multhi- ethnicity is an issue there which could instable the political system. Inclusivity is necessary for the stable and smooth running of the machinery. The UN special representative said to the Security Council that the current Taliban have excluded other ethnic groups from the political system in the government. The Taliban have occupied the whole of the country Afghanistan territory but they do not know how to tackle the issues of governance. On the one side, the internal disturbance is enough to divert their attention from the real purpose of governing the state of Afghanistan and on the other hand, there are reports of internal attacks on different parts of the country. This situation destabilizes the country's internal situation of the country.

Subsequently, the brain drain have posed serious challenges to the Emirates of Afghanistan. Now, looking at the state of Afghanistan, one of the most essential things in the running of the government machinery is the expertise and technocrats who know how to settle down multiple aspects of government and their problems. The technocrats and bureaucrats who were working in the previous regimes, were suspicious about the Taliban's attitude. Even though, Taliban have announced general amnesty for these experts and the personnel who were engaged in the running of the governmental machinery, but yet, the workers were not skeptical about this. It terrified them.

The looming threat is that the Taliban have promised to make such moves towards building political homogeneity and inclusiveness. Along with this, the intra-Afghan dialogues for having an inclusive nature of the government with other ethnicities halted the process of inclusive government. The nature in which the Taliban are acting is so precarious in this manner. They are not ready to hold talks with the other and major factions of the society. There seems no solid

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development in this regard. The other greater issue which the Taliban face is the recognition by the international communities. Today's world is a nation state which is to be gauged by certain measurements. The democratic ideals, rights of the citizens, political pluralism and inclusivity are the pinpoints which are considered to be essential for a nation state. The nations would be respected if they follow such ideals. The Taliban does not lie in the premises of these ideals which is a hurdle in their recognition.

Looking to the Afghan Taliban, they have been in the ruling for over three years now and the United Nations has showed its anger with the little progress made by the hardline group in various key areas. Expectedly, lack of rights for girls and women, as well as a soft stand on terrorism at the top the list. Addressing the United Nations Security Council on Tuesday, the multilateral body's deputy special representative for Afghanistan Markus Potzel presented that for many in the international community, "their patience is running out" with the Taliban. He furthered his view on to list the areas where the Taliban have performed little good, particularly pointing out the continued ban on girls' secondary education imposed by Afghanistan's rulers.

Findings

After thorough content analyses of the collected relevant data from secondary sources like research articles, newspaper articles and books, the researcher found various social, political and economic impacts of US-withdrawal from Afghanistan. After close analyses of the relevant contents, it was found out that the US-withdrawal and the subsequent Taliban take-over have resulted in various social, political and economic crises. The current research was delimited to exploring only humanitarian, political and economic impacts of US-withdrawal on Afghanistan. Therefore, the following are the major findings regarding the three major areas of the data analysis:

In this research, the humanitarian perspective was deeply looked upon in which the humanitarian condition in Afghanistan was the worst of all other challenges faced by the country in the post-US-withdrawal scenario. The data reveals that the hasty withdrawal of US from Afghanistan badly impacted the society of Afghanistan and led to worst humanitarian crises. The humans were living the life of animals. It was found that almost every welfare sector of the state is in a miserable condition. US withdrawal from Afghanistan led to poor health care system, food insecurity, deprivation of girls from education, violation of women's rights and malnourishment of the babies. The analysis of the relevant data shows that tens of thousands of girls have been deprived of secondary schools, while women have been barred from returning to many government jobs since the take-over of Afghan Taliban. It was revealed that people have sold their bodies and parts of bodies for the sake of survival.

The data analyses further reveal that various international institutions such as the UN and International Rescue Committee (IRC) and NGOs are playing some role in uplifting the common people out of the miserable condition by giving the emergency relief to various sections of the country but the data shows that such relief packages are insufficient to address the pathetic humanitarian conditions in the war-torn state. Overall, it was found that polarization of society, women's deprivation of their internationally sanctioned fundamental rights, food

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insecurity, worst malnutrition of children and poverty crises are the most significant social impact of US withdrawal from Afghanistan and the subsequent take-over of Taliban.

The invasion of Afghanistan by the US and her allies in the after math of 9/11 was more political oriented adventure than security concern. Therefore, the US withdrawal from Afghanistan without installing a stable and conclusive political government and the subsequent Taliban take-over have severe political impacts on Afghanistan. The data reveals that the US withdrew in haste from Afghanistan without establishing an organized and politically inclusive government and security force in Afghanistan that is the reason, the Taliban quickly took-over the charge of the country without much resistance from the national security forces. Therefore, the analyses of the relevant data show that the country was once again pushed to political turmoil and political disharmony. The analyses reveal that majority of the government and security official either fled the country or joined the Taliban and those who remained resistant were either executed or they fled to areas out of Taliban's control. The take-over of Taliban led the country to internal and external political crises: the Taliban established an autocratic and undemocratic government mainly staffed by the leaders of Taliban who are neither people's representative nor expert in running the government.

The analyses of the collected data from various sources shows that hasty withdrawal of US from Afghanistan and the subsequent take-over of Taliban led to various social and political disharmony, social and political polarization, establishment of autocratic government and ultimately to various humanitarian crises including violation of fundamental human right, brain- drainage, poverty and food insecurity. US withdrawal from Afghanistan resulted in the establishment of an autocratic Taliban government which adopted certain authoritarian measurements that made the international community skeptic about the political future of Afghanistan. The data reveals that the international community conditioned recognition of Taliban government and economic assistance with the protection of fundamental human rights by the Taliban government. Therefore, the US froze Afghan assets of about USD 10 billion. Similarly, the international community including international institutions like United Nations (UN), International Monetary Fund (IMF) and World Bank (WB) are also reluctant to extend any economic assistance to Taliban government. The data analyses further reveal that political instability, political polarization, poor law-and-order situation, unrecognized Taliban government, international sanctions on Taliban government and the presence of fanatic and extremist ISIS and TTP on Afghan soil are some of the fundamental obstructions to foreign investment in Afghanistan which further deteriorated the economic situation of the country.

Conclusion

Based upon the analyses of the collected data from various research articles, newspapers' articles and books and the findings of the analyses, Afghanistan remained a bone of contention either among its own local tribal chieftains or foreign invaders. The data analyses and findings confirm that every successive occupation of either foreign invaders or local tribes resulted in political instability, social polarization and economic degradation whether it was the

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USSR invasion and its withdrawal or the take-over of Taliban in 1996. Both were followed by extreme political instability to the extent of civil war, social crises including poverty, food insecurity, brain- drainage, and economic secession. The recent US invasion in 2001 after 9/11, the installation of US backed democratic government and the ultimate US withdrawal from Afghanistan are no exception to the pathetic social, political and economic conditions of the country.

The findings of the study confirm that US withdrew in haste without installing an inclusive and democratic political government, establishing a professional security force and creating intra- Afghan harmony which resulted in the immediate and easy take-over of Afghan Taliban. The Afghan Taliban established an autocratic government which made the international community skeptic about the political future of Afghanistan. Similarly, the findings confirm that Taliban violated human rights by banning girls from education and jobs and polarized the society by marginalizing various sects of Afghan society. Therefore, the findings validate that the international community did not extent their recognition to Taliban government which deteriorated the political conditions of the country. The findings further confirm that political instability led to economic degradation as the US froze Afghan assets, international institutions remained reluctant in providing economic assistance to Afghan government and foreign investment halted.

Resultantly, the pathetic economic conditions worsened living conditions in Afghanis because of food insecurity, unemployment, social polarization and disharmony. Although, the hasty US withdrawal caused severe social, political and economic crises in Afghanistan yet, the Taliban take-over can bear various social, political and economic prospects if they form an inclusive government by giving representation to all sects of Afghan society, maintain law-and-order, protect fundamental human right as recognized by international community, establish people- centered democratic government system and adopt a viable foreign policy.

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